

EDITORIAL MANAGEMENT

in Diamond Open Access publishing

Efficient and ethical publishing in Diamond Open Access relies on well-defined management processes.

Here are six key information a journal website should provide regarding its operational workflows, structural organisation, and administrative policies to ensure smooth functioning.

Clear aims and scope

- Journals need a clear definition of its objectives and subject coverage, and the reason for its existence.
- This guides the editorial team, informs potential readers and contributors, and enhances discoverability through search engines.
- It should be regularly reviewed and updated to ensure relevance.

Publishing schedule

- Journals must adhere to a realistic publishing schedule, whether traditional issue-based or continuous.
- Indexing services may not consider a journal for inclusion if it is not publishing on time.

Editorial team

- Roles and responsibilities of editors, editorial board and staff should be clearly defined.
- Editor-in-Chief and editorial board are usually recognized experts who guide the journal's strategy and provide subject expertise.
- Consider including a diverse range of editors to act as ambassadors and reflect the journal's quality.
- Names and affiliations of editorial board members should be publicly available.

Clear author guidelines

- These guidelines should outline criteria for articles (types allowed, submission and layout instructions, any journal-specifics) as well as policies on open access licensing, copyright, author fees, and publication ethics (also applicable to book publishing).

Data protection

- Adhering to data protection regulations like GDPR is essential for both journals and book publishers.
- GDPR aims to ensure transparency and inform EU users, workers, team members, about how your organisation uses, stores, and processes their personal data.
- Privacy notice should outline how your organisation processes personal data.

Digital preservation plan

- A preservation strategy is strongly recommended to safeguard content against loss or disruptions.
- Affordable solutions are available to ensure long-term preservation of journal and book content.

